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Better health, better futures

Innovations in Digital Technologies for Early Detection and Monitoring of Alzheimer's Dementia: From Speech to Circulatory Biomarkers

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Introduction

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a prevalent neurological disease affecting ageing populations

Causes (i.e. aetiology) are complex and variable.

The overwhelming majority incidence is sporadic and late onset.

The identification of biomarkers to screen for risk of developing AD and monitoring its progression is a vital part of improved understanding of the causes of AD and stratification of patients for treatments under development.

Speech as Biomarker

- Picture description task
- Fluency test
- Interviews conversations
- Audio signal is used in a number of automatic prediction tasks, including
 - cognitive state detection,
 - Presentation skills assessment
 - and emotion recognition.
- AD monitoring in resource constrained settings such as using raspberry pi.
- Preserving Privacy of users
 - Spoken content
 - Identity

Circulatory Biomarkers

Recent studies have demonstrated significant potential for blood plasma proteins to be used as cost effective biomarkers for AD in research and clinical practice.

Plasma A β biomarkers derived from an assay that combines immunoprecipitation techniques with mass spectrometry have been proposed which demonstrated high precision in predicting brain A β burden in relation to established AD biomarkers such as CSF A β 1–42 and A β PET [4].

Phosphorylated tau (pTau) forms can also be detected in blood plasma (as well as in CSF) at different sites through high-accuracy mass spectrometry and immunoassays.

Neurofilament light chain protein (NfL) and glial fibrillary acid protein (GFAP) blood plasma based biomarkers have also been investigated.

Circulatory Biomarkers

We assess the predictive accuracy of machine learning methods to diagnose and predict risk of developing AD using human blood plasma and CSF biomarkers.

In particular, we examine the potential of the blood biomarker panel containing 164 blood plasma proteins,

in comparison and combination with CSF biomarkers.

An accurate biomarker panel based solely on blood plasma could potentially contribute to a better understanding of AD pathophysiology and provide more cost-effective and accessible biomarkers for drug trials and clinical practice.

Privacy-based Data Collection System: Hardware

- Matrix Creator board, consisting of a microphone array, an inertial measurement unit, and several other sensors,
- Raspberry Pi 3 B+

Figure 1: *Matrix Creator and Raspberry Pi 3 B+*

- This setup is meant to be installed in room where social activity and dialogue interaction occurs most frequently, such as a dining room or a sitting room.

Acoustics Data Collection System: Software

- For voice activity detection, we employed the Auditok Python binding.
- the OpenSMILE toolkit and a user recognition module are used to process the audio file and save the speech features in the attribute-relation file format (ARFF).

System Demo

Speech Data-Set:

- Pitt Corpora Sub-set selection
- Circulatory Biomarkers

BASIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PATIENTS IN EACH GROUP.

Age Interval	AD		non-AD	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
[50, 55)	2	1	2	1
[55, 60)	7	8	7	8
[60, 65)	4	9	4	9
[65, 70)	10	14	10	14
[70, 75)	9	11	9	11
[75, 80)	4	3	4	3
Total	36	46	36	46

NUMBERS OF PATIENTS PER DIAGNOSTIC/BIOMARKERS (TOP) AND PROGNOSTIC (BOTTOM); SEX AND MEAN AGE IN BRACKETS.

Dataset	AD	NC	MCI		
Blood	158 (68♀, 75.4; 90♂, 76.5)	61 (29♀, 76.7; 32♂, 75)	275 (92♀, 75.5; 183♂, 77.1)		
Blood+CSF	106 (43♀, 74.6; 63♂, 77.5)	49 (22♀, 77.2; 27♂, 75.1)	113 (34♀, 74.2; 79♂, 77.9)		
Prognosis (disease progression from baseline)					
AD-AD	AD-MCI	MCI-AD	MCI-MCI	MCI-NC	NC-NC
95	1	63	274	7	54

- 2033 speech segments from 82 non-AD subjects and 2043 speech segments from 82 AD
- 2033 speech segments from 82 non-AD subjects and 2043 speech segments from 82 AD

Feature Sets

- **Speech Features**

- Three features sets are extracted which have been widely used
 - emotion recognition,
 - eating conditions recognition
 - and cognitive state detection.
- emobase:
- ComParE
- eGeMAPS

F. Eyben, M. Wollmer, and B. Schuller, “openSMILE: the Munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor,” in Procs. of ACMMM. ACM, 2010, pp. 1459–1462.

- **Circulatory features**

- 14 Plasma (Das et al.)
- 164 Plasma
- CSF
- CSF+Plasma

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Results : Acoustic Features

ADR CLASSIFICATION RESULTS WITH NUMBER OF CLUSTERS (m) USED. THE CHANCE LEVEL IS 50.00%

Features	LDA, m	DT, m	1NN, m	SVM, m	RF, m
emobase	56.10, 30	66.46, 20	54.88, 80	45.12, 15	60.98, 25
ComParE	57.93, 35	68.90, 95	55.49, 100	59.76, 35	60.37, 95
eGeMAPS	77.44 , 85	71.34, 30	54.27, 65	52.44, 20	71.34, 30
MRCG	59.76, 5	69.51, 15	52.44, 95	59.76, 15	63.41, 15
mean	62.81	69.05	54.27	54.27	64.03

Fusion

Output Class	nonAD	63 38.4%	16 9.8%	79.7% 20.3%
	AD	19 11.6%	66 40.2%	77.6% 22.4%
		76.8% 23.2%	80.5% 19.5%	78.7% 21.3%
		nonAD	AD	
		Target Class		

Results: AD diagnosis

TABLE II

MODEL PERFORMANCE ON THE AD DIAGNOSIS TASK (AUC VALUES).

Biomarkers	Method	Biomarkers only		Biomarkers, age, sex	
		CV	Test	CV	Test
14 plasma	Adaboost	0.854	0.714	0.889	0.764
146 plasma	SVM	0.938	0.820	0.939	0.823
CSF	KNN	0.984	0.947	0.983	0.947
CSF+Plasma	SVM	0.986	0.985	0.985	0.941

Results: AD prognosis

TABLE III

MODEL PERFORMANCE ON THE AD PROGNOSIS TASK (UAR VALUES).

Biomarkers	Method	Biomarkers only		Biomarkers, age, sex	
		CV	Test	CV	Test
14 plasma	DT	0.445	0.383	0.424	0.344
146 plasma	SVM	0.620	0.619	0.627	0.623
CSF	DT	0.622	0.607	0.607	0.607
CSF+Plasma	Adaboost	0.654	0.613	0.648	0.613

Conclusion

Demonstrates the relevance of acoustic features and affective behaviour of spontaneous speech for cognitive impairment detection in the context of Alzheimer's Disease diagnosis.

Demonstrate the discrimination power of CSF and blood plasma protein for diagnosis and prognosis of AD

Machine learning methods operating on automatically extracted voice features provide accuracy of up to 78.7%, well above the chance level of 50% while a combination of CSF and blood achieved an accuracy of greater than 88.0 %.

Provides a route to AD diagnosis and prognosis which is as good or better than current and recent approaches

This also provides a route to unbiased discovery of interactomes augmenting understanding of the disease.

Introduced Shared Task

Alzheimer's Dementia Recognition through Spontaneous Speech: The ADRess Challenge INTERSPEECH 2020

Detecting cognitive decline using speech only: The addresso challenge INTERSPEECH 2021

ADReSS-M Multilingual alzheimer's dementia recognition through spontaneous speech: a signal processing grand challenge ICASSP 2023

Connected Speech-Based Cognitive Assessment in Chinese and English INTERSPEECH2024

The Prediction and Recognition of Cognitive Decline through Spontaneous Speech, Signal Processing Grand Challenge (PROCESS) ICASSP 2025

AReSS-M Challenge (English and Greek language)

AD detection accuracy results.

AReSS-M Challenge (English and Greek language)

MMSE regression results.

TAUKADIAL 2024 Challenge (English and Chinese language)

TAUKADIAL 2024 Challenge (English and Chinese language)

Future Work

SIDE-AD Study funded under Sony Research Award

Speech being collected from participant drawn from PREVENT cohort (~ 450 subjects for longitudinal speech data)

A direct comparison of speech and EHR from the same population

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